

Fermat's last theorem: For the case where $n \mid XYZ$

(n is a prime number bigger than 2 and the exponent of the Fermat equation)

All characters in this paper are natural numbers.

Author Eunho Lee

Affiliation Chungang University

Email 1019leeunho@naver.com

eternuce@cau.ac.kr

[Abstract]

For coprime natural number ordered pairs (X,Y,Z) , two or more of X,Y , and Z cannot be multiples of n .

If X is a multiple of n , we can derive that

$$Z - Y = n^{kn-1}L^n$$

$$Z - X = R^n$$

$$X + Y = G^n$$

If we solve and simplify the three equation above,

$$Z = \frac{G^n + R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}$$

$$Y = \frac{G^n + R^n - n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}$$

$$X = \frac{G^n - R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}$$

1. So if X is a multiple of n , the ordered pair of the Fermat equation must satisfy the following form:

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2} \right) = (n^k LB, RA, GC)$$

Where n is a prime number (index of the Fermat equation), and G,R,L,A,B,C are all coprime natural numbers.

By same way,

2. If Y is a multiple of n, the ordered pair of the Fermat equation must satisfy the following form:

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - n^{kn-1}R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + n^{kn-1}R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + n^{kn-1}R^n + L^n}{2} \right) = (LB, n^k RA, GC)$$

Where n is a prime number (index of the Fermat equation), and G,R,L,A,B,C are all coprime natural numbers.

3. If Z is a multiple of n, the ordered pair of the Fermat equation must satisfy the following form:

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{n^{kn-1}G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{n^{kn-1}G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{n^{kn-1}G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right) = (RA, LB, n^k GC)$$

Where n is a prime number (index of the Fermat equation), and G,R,L,A,B,C are all coprime natural numbers.

The reason for the above ordered pairs 1,2,3 hold will be explained later, but the core reason follows the logic written in the previous paper.

<https://zenodo.org/records/17295783>

And then, we will derive a contradiction in the form of each ordered pair 1,2,3.

By comparing the even and odd values of variables G,R, and L.

For example, in the case 2, if $(G,R,L)=(\text{odd},\text{odd},\text{even})$,

We can calculate

$$G^n + L^n = (G + L)(G^{n-1} - G^{n-2}L + \dots - GL^{n-2} + L^{n-1}) = (\text{odd natural number})$$

(because $G^n + L^n = (\text{odd}) + (\text{even}) = (\text{odd})$).

And also we can let

$$G^n - L^n = (G - L)((G^{n-1} + G^{n-2}L + \dots + GL^{n-2} + L^{n-1}) = (\text{odd natural number})$$

(because $G^n - L^n = (\text{odd}) - (\text{even}) = (\text{odd})$. And why $G^n - L^n > 0$? Because,

$$X + Y = G^n$$

$$Z - Y = L^n$$

If we subtract the equation below from the top,

$$X + 2Y - Z = G^n - L^n > 0 \quad (\because X + Y > Z)$$

And we will derive contradiction by using algebraic methods. By letting

$$G + L = 2m - 1$$

(m is an arbitrary natural number, because $G + L = (\text{odd})$).

$$G - L = 2k - 1$$

(k is an arbitrary natural number, because $G^n - L^n = (\text{odd}) > 0$, so $G > L$).

Then, if we add the two equation above,

$$2G = 2m + 2k - 2$$

$$G = m + k - 1$$

If we subtract the two equations above,

$$2L = 2m - 2k$$

$$L = m - k$$

Now, we can use the fact that in case 2,

$$L \mid Y$$

That is,

$$(m - k) \mid Y$$

$$\rightarrow (m - k) \mid \frac{G^n + n^{kn-1}R^n - L^n}{2} = \left(\frac{G^n + n^{kn-1}R^n - (m - k)^n}{2} \right)$$

Because $L=m-k$

$$\rightarrow 2(m - k) \mid \{G^n + n^{kn-1}R^n - (m - k)^n\}$$

And since $G = m + k - 1$,

if $\gcd(m, k) = 1$, we can express $R = u_1m + u_2k$ for suitable integers u_1, u_2 .

Then,

$$2(m - k) \mid \{(m + k - 1)^n + n^{kn-1}(u_1m + u_2k)^n + (m - k)^n\}$$

The right-hand side must always be a multiple of $(m-k)$.

Therefore if we substitute $m=k$, the right-hand side must become 0.

$$0 = (2k - 1)^n + n^{kn-1}(u_1k + u_2k)^n$$

$$-n^{kn-1}\{k(u_1 + u_2)\}^n = (2k - 1)^n$$

While the right-hand side is n squared, the left-hand cannot be n squared.

So this is contradiction.

If $\gcd(m, k) > 1$, we can express $R = v_1k + v_2(k - 1)$ for suitable integers v_1, v_2 .

Because $\gcd(k, k - 1) = 1$. ($k > 2$, the case where $k=1$ will be discussed below.

Then we will show that the expression $R = v_1k + v_2(k - 1)$ leads to a contradiction for any integers v_1, v_2 .

$$2(m - k) \mid \{(m + k - 1)^n + n^{kn-1}(v_1k + v_2(k - 1))^n + (m - k)^n\}$$

Since the right-hand side must always be a multiple of $(m-k)$, if we substitute $m=k$, the right-hand side must become 0.

$$0 = \{(2k - 1)^n + n^{kn-1}(v_1k + v_2k - 1)^n\}$$

$$(2k - 1)^n = -n^{kn-1}(v_1k + v_2k - 1)^n$$

The left-hand side is n squared, but the right-hand side cannot be a n squared.

Therefore this equation is contradiction.

Lastly, if $k=1$, then

$$G = m, \quad L = m - 1, \quad R = v_1$$

$$2(m - 1) \mid \{m^n + n^{kn-1}(v_1)^n + (m - 1)^n\}$$

Substitute $m=1$, then the right-hand side must become 0.

$$1^n + n^{kn-1}(v_1)^n = 0$$

This is impossible. Because $n > 2$.

Therefore $k > 2$.

Auxiliary 1.

If n is a prime number, then nCr is always a multiple of n . (r is a natural number that satisfies $0 < r < n$)

$$n \mid \binom{n}{r}$$

Pf)

$$nCr = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{(n-r)! \times r!}$$

Since r is a natural number and $0 < r < n$,

$$(n-r) < n$$

$$r < n$$

And since n is a prime number, $(n-r)!$ cannot divide n .

Also $r!$ cannot divide n .

If $(n-r)!$ or $r!$ can divide n , it means that n is divisible by natural numbers smaller than n . (except 1, n)

Auxiliary2.

When all variables are natural numbers, the following equation is contradiction.

$$nk = n^2m$$
$$n \nmid k, n \nmid m$$

This is because the left-hand side merely a multiple of n , while the right-hand side is a multiple of n squared.

If we divide both sides by n ,

$$k = nm$$

k is not a multiple of n , But the right-hand side is a multiple of n .

So we can know that this is a contradiction

Auxiliary3.

If there is even one ordered pair of natural numbers (X,Y,Z) in Fermat's equation, there also naturally exist coprime natural number ordered pairs (x,y,z) .

So we discuss ordered pairs of coprime natural numbers (X,Y,Z) .

If (X,Y,Z) are a disjoint ordered pair, there is no case where only y and z have a common prime factor p ($p > 1$). If there exists a common prime factor p between y and z , then x must also have p as a common prime factor.

Pf) Let's assume that Y and Z are multiples of p , and X is not a multiple of p .

We can let $(X,Y,Z) = (X,py,pz)$

$$X^n + (py)^n = (pz)^n$$

$$X^n = p^n z^n - p^n y^n$$

$$X^n = p^n (z^n - y^n)$$

Since the right-hand side is a multiple of p , the left-hand side also must be a multiple of p .

But we assumed that X is not a multiple of p .

It is contradiction. Therefore we can conclude that if (X,Y,Z) are a disjoint ordered pair, there is no case where only y and z have a common prime factor p ($p > 1$).

Or X and Y are multiples of p , X and Z are multiples of p are all impossible.

Auxiliary4. Fermat's little theorem

When n is a prime number and a is not a multiple of n ,

$$a^n \equiv a \pmod{n}$$

Chapter A. Let's consider the case where X is a multiple of n.

(By Auxiliary3, only one of X,Y, and Z can be a multiple of n.)

$$(X, Y, Z) = (nx, Y, Z)$$

Then why does the following hold true?

$$Z - X = R^n \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$Z - Y = n^{kn-1}L^n \text{ ----- (2)}$$

$$X + Y = G^n \text{ ----- (3)}$$

$$(1), Z - X = R^n$$

First, if we suppose that

$$X = Z - p$$

p is an arbitrary prime number, but not a multiple of n.

If $n \mid p$, since we supposed that $n \mid X$,

$$Z = X - p = (\text{multiple of } n)$$

Therefore $n \mid Z$.

It is contradiction by Auxiliary3.

Then the ordered pair $(X,Y,Z)=(Z-p,Y,Z)$

Substitute $(Z-p,Y,Z)$ into the Fermat equation.

$$(Z - p)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}p + \binom{n}{2}Z^{n-2}p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}Z^2p^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1}Zp^{n-1} - p^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides is canceled out.

Then all terms except Y^n are multiples of p .

Therefore Y must also be a multiple of p .

$$Y = py$$

y is a suitable natural number.

Then,

$$Y^n = p^n y^n$$

The equation changes as follows.

$$-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}p + \binom{n}{2}Z^{n-2}p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}Z^2p^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1}Zp^{n-1} - p^n + p^n y^n = 0$$

Now, all terms except $-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}p$ are multiples of p^2 .

If $p \mid Z$, $\gcd(Y, Z) = p > 1$. It is impossible because we are finding coprime X, Y, Z .

By auxiliary 3, there must be no common prime factor between Y and Z .

Therefore, this equation is contradiction by Auxiliary 2.

And we can conclude that for all prime numbers p , (except n) all cases where

$$X = Z - p$$

is impossible.

Then how about this case?

$$X = Z - p^2$$

By similar way, when we substitute $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p^2, Y, Z)$ and expand them, we can reach the conclusion that Y must be a multiple of p .

$$-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}p^2 + \binom{n}{2}Z^{n-2}p^4 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}Z^2p^{2(n-2)} + \binom{n}{n-1}Zp^{2(n-1)} - p^{2n} + Y^n = 0$$

All terms except Y^n are multiples of p^2 .

$p \mid Y$ is sufficient. Y does not need to be a multiple of p^2 .

And $p \mid Y$ means that $p^n \mid Y^n$.

If we substitute $Y^n = p^n y^n$ above, all terms except $-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}p^2$ are multiples of p^4 . ($\because n \geq 3$)

And since $p \nmid Z$ because Y is already a multiple of p , this equation is contradiction by Auxiliary 2.

Therefore for all prime numbers p , (except n) all cases where

$$X = Z - p^2$$

is impossible.

This chain of regularity continues until

$$X = Z - p^n$$

In this relationship, we cannot find any contradiction by Auxiliary2.

How about other case? For example, for another prime number q , (q is not n)

$$X = Z - p^n q$$

Let's substitute $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p^n q, Y, Z)$ and expand it.

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^n q + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^{2n} q^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{(n-2)n} q^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{(n-1)n} q^{n-1} - p^{n^2} q^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

The Z^n on both sides is canceled out and disappears.

Then, all terms except Y^n are multiples of $p^n q$.

Therefore $p q \mid Y$ and $p^n q^n \mid Y^n$.

We can let

$$Y^n = p^n q^n y^n, (y \text{ is a suitable natural number})$$

$$-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}p^nq + \binom{n}{2}Z^{n-2}q^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}Z^2p^{(n-2)n}q^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1}Zp^{(n-1)n}q^{n-1} - p^{n^2}q^n + p^nq^n y^n = 0$$

Then, all terms except $-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}p^nq$ are multiples of p^nq^2 .

Since $n \nmid pq$, Z must be a multiple of q .

But Y is already a multiple of q . Therefore this equation is contradiction by Auxiliary2.

By similar way, $X = Z - p^nq^2$ is impossible.

Only when the form $X = Z - p^nq^n$ is satisfied, there is not a contradiction in the equation.

And by similar way again, for another prime number r , (r is not n)

$$X = Z - p^nq^n r$$

$$X = Z - p^nq^n r^2$$

⋮

All of the above relationships result in a contradiction.

Only when the form $X = Z - p^nq^n r^n$ is satisfied, there is not a contradiction in the equation.

In conclusion, to generalize, for some prime numbers $p_i, (i \in \mathbb{N})$

A contradiction by Auxiliary2 does not arise only when the relation satisfies the following form.

$$X = Z - p_1^n p_2^n p_3^n \dots p_i^n$$

And extending this a little further, a contradiction by Auxiliary2 does not arise only when p_i is the square of a multiple of n .

For $k_i, i \in \mathbb{N}$

$$X = Z - p_1^{k_1 n} p_2^{k_2 n} p_3^{k_3 n} \dots p_i^{k_i n}$$

For example, $X = Z - 2^n 5^{2n} 101^{8n}$ is allowed.

In a word, $Z-X$ must be in the form of some natural number raised to the power of n .

$$Z - X = R^n \text{ --- (1)}$$

R is a suitable natural number, and not a multiple of n .

$$(2), Z - Y = n^{kn-1}L^n$$

Now, let's derive (2), $Z - Y = n^{kn-1}L^n$.

First of all, why $(Z-Y)$ must be a multiple of n ?

Because we assumed that X is a multiple of n . Therefore Y and Z are not a multiple of n .
(By Auxiliary3)

In the equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$, since n is a prime number,

Following relationships are satisfied by Fermat' little theorem.

$$X^n \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$$

$$Y^n \equiv Y \pmod{n}$$

$$Z^n \equiv Z \pmod{n}$$

Since $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$, the following must naturally hold true.

$$X^n + Y^n \equiv Z^n \pmod{n}$$

$$Y^n \equiv Z^n \pmod{n}$$

$$Y \equiv Z \pmod{n}$$

$$\therefore Z - Y \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$$

We can let $Z - Y = np$. For a suitable prime number p .

$$Y = Z - np$$

$$(X, Y, Z) = (nx, Z - np, Z)$$

$$(nx)^n + (Z - np)^n = Z^n$$

$$n^n x^n + Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} np + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} n^2 p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 n^{n-2} p^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z n^{n-1} p^{n-1} - n^n p^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides is canceled out.

$$n^n x^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} np + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} n^2 p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 n^{n-2} p^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z n^{n-1} p^{n-1} - n^n p^n = 0 \text{ ----- } (\mathcal{H})$$

And then, by Auxiliary1, $\binom{n}{r}$ are multiples of n .

So in the equation (\mathcal{H}) , all terms except $-\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} np$ are multiples of n^3 .

Since Z cannot be a multiple of n , it is contradiction by Auxiliary2.

$Y = Z - np$ is impossible. n must have a higher degree exponent.

Also, p must have a higher degree exponent. Because in the equation (\mathcal{H}) , all terms except $n^n x^n$ are multiples of p . Therefore X must be a multiple of p .

$$X = npx$$

p also must have a higher degree exponent until the exponent becomes a multiple of n .

By previous way, only the form that

$$Y = Z - n^{n-1} p^n$$

If we extend this form as much as possible to the general form that does not result in a contradiction according to Auxiliary2,

$$Y = Z - n^{kn-1} p_1^{r_1 n} p_2^{r_2 n} p_3^{r_3 n} \dots p_i^{r_i n}$$

For prime numbers $p_i, i \in \mathbb{N}$

And suitable natural numbers $r_i, i \in \mathbb{N}$

And natural number k.

As a result, we can get a form that

$$Y = Z - n^{kn-1} L^n - - - - - (2)$$

L is not a multiple of n, and L is coprime to R. ($Z - X = R^n$)

Why $\gcd(R, L) = 1$?

$Z - X = R^n$ induces Y to be a multiple of R.

$$Y = Ry$$

$Z - Y = n^{kn-1} L^n$ induces X to be a multiple of $n^k L$.

$$X = n^k Lx$$

If $\gcd(R, L) = q > 1$, it means that $\gcd(X, Y) = q > 1$.

It is impossible by Auxiliary3.

$$(3), X + Y = G^n$$

Suppose that $X + Y = p$. p is a prime number and $p \neq n$.

If $p = n$, in the equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$,

$$X^n + Y^n = (X + Y)\{X^{n-1} - X^{n-2}Y + X^{n-3}Y^2 - \dots + X^2Y^{n-3} - XY^{n-2} + Y^{n-1}\}$$

Therefore $(X + Y) \mid Z^n$

$$p \mid Z$$

If p is a multiple of n , it is impossible because X is already a multiple of n .

Therefore $X + Y = p$ and $n \nmid p$.

$$X = p - Y$$

$$Z = pz (\because (X + Y) \mid Z^n)$$

$$(X, Y, Z) = (p - Y, Y, pz)$$

$$(p - Y)^n + Y^n = (pz)^n$$

Since n is a prime number that $n \geq 3$,

$$p^n - \binom{n}{1}p^{n-1}Y + \binom{n}{2}p^{n-2}Y^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}p^2Y^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1}pY^{n-1} - Y^n + Y^n = p^n z^n$$

$-Y^n + Y^n$ are canceled out.

$$p^n - \binom{n}{1}p^{n-1}Y + \binom{n}{2}p^{n-2}Y^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}p^2Y^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1}pY^{n-1} = p^n Z^n$$

All terms except $\binom{n}{n-1}pY^{n-1}$ are multiples of p^2 .

But Y cannot be a multiple of p because Z is already a multiple of p .

Therefore the equation above is contradiction by Auxiliary2.

And again, $X + Y = p$ is impossible.

By similar way like ChapterA – (1), (2),

The exponent of p must be increased until the exponent becomes a multiple of n .

$$X + Y = p^{kn}$$

If we further expand this form,

$$X + Y = p_1^{r_1 n} p_2^{r_2 n} p_3^{r_3 n} \dots p_i^{r_i n} = (p_1^{r_1} p_2^{r_2} p_3^{r_3} \dots p_i^{r_i})^n$$

p_i are distinct prime numbers.

r_i are suitable natural numbers.

$$X + Y = G^n \text{ --- (3)}$$

(In this case, $G = p_1^{r_1} p_2^{r_2} p_3^{r_3} \dots p_i^{r_i}$)

It induces to Z^n be a multiple of G^n .

It means that $G \mid Z$.

$$Z = Gz$$

Chapter 8.

We derived the relationship equations (1), (2), (3).

$$Z - X = R^n \text{ --- (1)}$$

$$Z - Y = n^{kn-1}L^n \text{ --- (2)}$$

$$X + Y = G^n \text{ --- (3)}$$

Additionally, (1), (2), (3) induces that

$$Y = Ry$$

$$X = n^kLx$$

$$Z = Gz$$

(All characters are coprime each other.)

Add (1) and (2)

$$2Z - X - Y = R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n$$

Since (3), substitute $X + Y = G^n$

$$2Z - G^n = R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n$$

$$2Z = G^n + R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n$$

$$\therefore Z = \frac{G^n + R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}$$

Substitute this Z into the equation (1).

$$\frac{G^n + R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2} - X = R^n$$

$$\therefore X = \frac{G^n - R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}$$

Substitute Z into the equation (2)

$$\frac{G^n + R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2} - Y = n^{kn-1}L^n$$

$$\therefore Y = \frac{G^n + R^n - n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}$$

To summarize,

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - n^{kn-1}L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + n^{kn-1}L^n}{2} \right)$$

And the following form also must be satisfied:

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Ry, n^k Lx, Gz)$$

So we were able to verify that the initial equation on abstract 1. is correct.

How about check 2. – Y is a multiple of n . or 3. – Z is a multiple of n ?

In fact, X and Y can be swapped. Because

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

If you change the order adding X^n and Y^n , nothing changes.

If 2. – Y is multiple of n , we can let Y as case 1. – X is multiple of n .

And the properties that the case $n \mid X$ must satisfy must be equally satisfied by the case $n \mid Y$.

Therefore the form of case 2. is true.

How about the case 3. - $n \mid Z$?

Let

$$X + Y = np$$

Then $X = np - Y$

Substitute and expand and check Auxiliary2.

Then we can find that the exponent of n must be increased until the exponent is $kn - 1$.

And the exponent of p must be increased until multiple of n .

Therefore $X + Y = n^{kn-1}G^n$ and

$$Z - X = R^n$$

$$Z - Y = L^n$$

So we can get the conclusion that the form of case 3. Is true.